

FOSTERING INNOVATION THROUGH OPEN SCIENCE

A cross-sector roadmap
for impact

Prepared by

Open Research
Community Accelerator

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About ORCA and This Briefing

The Open Research Community Accelerator ([ORCA](#)) is a non-profit focused on making science more engaging, accessible, and actionable. ORCA prides itself on being a “doing shop” rather than a “talking shop,” with an emphasis on tangible outcomes and meaningful impact. We have a unique ability to build inclusive, big-tent coalitions that transcend boundaries—whether geographic, disciplinary, sectoral, or career-stage, creating spaces where diverse voices converge to drive innovation and action.

We are proud to partner with a diverse range of organizations to advance our mission, including NSF, NASA, UNESCO, CERN, Science Europe, the Gordon & Betty Moore Foundation, the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation, Schmidt Sciences, the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, the University of California’s Haas School of Business, Georgetown University’s Center for Security and Emerging Technology, the Academic Data Science Alliance, and the Belmont Forum. More on ORCA programs and activities may be found [here](#).

This briefing constitutes the first stage of the “Fostering Innovation Network” (FIN) project by ORCA. FIN will explore practical ways to leverage the potential of open science, open source, and open data to fuel innovation, accelerate discovery, power AI breakthroughs, catalyze economic growth, and drive societal progress.

In this context, the goal of this report is to brief readers on some of the most salient economic and societal benefits of open science practices and policies today. We aim to synthesize real world evidence that makes a compelling case for open science as a driver of science, technology and innovation. To make it easier for industry and funders to see themselves in this work, we provide specific callouts within each section highlighting key takeaways.

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Executive Summary	03
The Strategic Imperative of Open Science	04
Open Science in Action: Use Cases and Return on Investment	06
Promoting Societal Change Challenges	16 22
Strategic Opportunities	24
Call to Action	28
Glossary of Terms	29
References	31

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Open science—the practice of making research practices and outputs more transparent and accessible— is a key strategy for driving innovation, stimulating economic growth, powering economic opportunities, and advancing societal progress. While broad adoption is still emerging, open science is accelerating the translation of discoveries into practical applications by upskilling the global R&D ecosystem and creating new avenues for entrepreneurship, public-private partnerships, and faster, more efficient innovation across interdisciplinary fields, such as artificial intelligence, biotechnology, and climate science.

Open science also strengthens the relationship between research and society. Transparent and participatory practices enhance public trust, improve accountability, and expand who can engage with and benefit from scientific knowledge—supporting a more inclusive and responsive research environment. The result is a self-reinforcing cycle that can improve the relevance, timeliness, and quality of research. The unfettered distribution of better research, in turn, creates the conditions that spur the innovations that generate public value, including economic opportunity and breakthrough technologies.

This briefing presents several use cases in both the public and private sectors, demonstrating how open science can generate a greater return on investment. It also outlines approaches for implementing an open science strategy in various contexts. This is intended for private funders, academic researchers, industry leaders, and policymakers who want to understand how integrating open science can more effectively advance their missions. The briefing concludes with a call to action to coordinate strategies, infrastructure, policies, and partnerships that integrate open science into long-term planning for all organizations.

“Open science is not merely about expanding access to knowledge—it’s about designing an intentional approach to R&D that is more efficient, connected, resilient, and responsive to the challenges and opportunities of our time.”

The Strategic Imperative of Open Science

In recent years, organizations as far-ranging as [UNESCO](#), [OECD](#), the [European Commission](#), and the [US federal government](#) have made open science a strategic priority. Historically, open science efforts have focused on academic outputs—open access publishing and data sharing—which have indeed boosted transparency and collaboration within the research community. But there is potential for greater impact beyond academic research.

Open science promises benefits in several domains; in the last few years evidence shows progress in some of these areas. In [academia](#), it removes barriers to knowledge access, enabling researchers worldwide to build on existing findings, reproduce results, and collaborate more effectively. [Socially](#), it contributes to democratizing knowledge, better empowering researchers and communities to effectively engage in, and with, science. [Economically](#), open science lowers costs by minimizing paywall dependencies and streamlining publicly funded research dissemination, offering taxpayers a greater return on investment.

The full strategic value of open science lies in its ability to forge connections across academia, industry and civil society. Open source, often mentioned in association with open science, has its own ethos, practices and history that are key for unlocking this potential.

Open source has already demonstrated its capacity to drive innovation, scalability, and economic growth in the private sector. By more fully integrating open-source principles into open science frameworks—such as reusable code, shared tools, and community-driven development—open science can better seize new avenues for applied research, public-private partnerships, and rapid knowledge translation. This shift would not only accelerate scientific progress but also catalyze broader societal progress, positioning open science as a practical enabler of sustainable innovation and more inclusive growth.

The sections that follow make this case by focusing on the broad socioeconomic impacts of open science. We address these in two ways: enablements—how open science unlocks new, high-impact activities—and efficiencies—how it achieves equal or greater outcomes with fewer resources. We also account for the socioeconomic benefits in terms of public trust and accountability in research, transparency and civic society engagement. The evidence we present is obtained from case studies using surveys, interviews, desk research on costs/benefits, or combinations of those methods.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

Open science drives competitive advantage through rapid knowledge translation (e.g. Watson OpenScale), public-private partnerships (e.g. Structural Genomics Consortium), and access to cutting-edge tools. It lowers barriers for SMEs and startups, enabling them to compete with established players.

FOR FUNDERS

Open science aligns with mandates for equitable access, public trust and measurable societal impact. Initiatives like UNESCO's Open Science Recommendation and the EU's Open Science Cloud demonstrate its growing relevance in global research policy frameworks.

OPEN SCIENCE IN ACTION:

USE CASES AND RETURN ON INVESTMENT

Accelerating Research Efficiency and Discovery

Open science drives its most profound bursts of innovation through three core patterns. First, the elimination of redundant R&D efforts through open data and tools saves years of foundational work, as seen in genomics ([Alphafold](#)) and AI ([PyTorch](#)). Second, rapid industry adoption occurs when [open resources lower barriers to entry](#)—over 70% of AI startups now build on open models, while semiconductor firms like NVIDIA leverage [RISC-V](#) to bypass proprietary licensing. Third, cost reductions materialize through open hardware ([Open Compute Project \(OCP\)](#)) and agile infrastructure in the space industry ([OpenCosmos](#)), expanding access to advanced technologies. As an example, after Microsoft joined OCP, it [reported](#) up to 40% server cost savings, 15% power efficiency gains and a 50% reduction in deployment and service times.

These patterns collectively demonstrate how openness accelerates innovation timelines, scales solutions faster, and [redirects resources toward applied problems](#) rather than reinventing basic frameworks. This shift is observable across sectors, where previously high-cost initiatives are now progressing through global collaboration and shared infrastructure.

RISC-V (pronounced “risk-five”) is an open, royalty-free standard for how a computer’s processor understands and executes instructions. It opens the blueprint or “language” that tells a chip what to do—fetch data, perform calculations, move information around and more.

RISC-V International is the global non-profit home of the open standard RISC-V Instruction Set Architecture (ISA), related specifications, and stakeholder community. More than 4,500 RISC-V members across 70 countries contribute and collaborate to define RISC-V open specifications as well as convene and govern related technical, industry, domain, and special interest groups.

RISC-V enables the community to share technical investment, contribute to the strategic future, create more rapidly, enjoy unprecedented design freedom, and substantially reduce the cost of innovation.

Open science optimizes the return on investment in research and development by minimizing the friction inherent in closed systems. Paywalls and proprietary restrictions often limit the dissemination and utility of research, whereas open frameworks encourage [broader participation and reuse](#). In biology and medicine, for example, [inventors use 73% and 27% more open access](#) publications, respectively, compared to closed-access ones.

Complex challenges are fertile ground for open science. The [PAT4CGT](#) consortium brings together public and private [partners](#) in cell and gene therapy (CGT) to co-develop predictive tools and digital twins for advanced therapy manufacturing. In the AI domain, IBM uses [open approaches](#) to enhance governance, trust, and transparency [across its AI systems](#). By open-sourcing models like [Granite](#), IBM fosters collaboration and accelerates responsible innovation.

Small enterprises and researchers can leverage openly available datasets—such as those provided by space agencies or public health institutions—to drive innovation without requiring expensive infrastructure. [Evidence suggests](#) that open access mandates correlate with increased patent filings derived from academic work, indicating more effective pathways to commercialization.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

Open approaches lead to significant cost savings—like Microsoft’s 40% reduction in server costs through the Open Compute Project—and faster innovation cycles, as seen in NVIDIA’s deployment of a billion RISC-V cores. They also provide access to pre-competitive research, enabling breakthroughs through shared platforms and datasets like ImageNet or collaborative consortiums in pharma.

FOR FUNDERS

Openness boosts the visibility and impact of funded research while reducing duplication, ensuring more efficient use of resources. It also encourages interdisciplinary collaboration, which can accelerate progress on complex, cross-cutting challenges.

Optimizing Investment: Cost Savings and Productivity Gains

There are a [range of efficiency benefits](#) associated with open science, particularly in the form of access cost savings, labour productivity gains, and reduced transaction costs. Open access publishing and data repositories substantially lower the financial burden for both researchers and commercial users by removing paywalls and licensing barriers. For example, shifting to open access models in the UK higher education sector [could generate annual savings](#) of £80–116 million, with individual articles costing up to £1,180 less than those under subscription models.

Data repositories such as the Economic and Social Data Service (ESDS) and the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI) provide additional value, with user [willingness-to-pay estimates](#) exceeding operational costs by factors of five or six. Although precise valuations are difficult due to methodological challenges and the blending of research and government data, these findings indicate that [open infrastructures](#) deliver significant economic value by reducing the costs of accessing and sharing research outputs.

Highlights

[OpenFold](#) is a non-profit AI research and development consortium developing free and open-source software tools for biology and drug discovery. It aims to democratize the power of biological AI and lead a community-driven effort to make advanced protein structure prediction tools available to researchers and scientists in academia, biotech and pharmaceutical companies across the globe.

Open science also improves productivity by decreasing the time required to access and use research findings. A [study](#) in Denmark showed that researchers can lose nearly an hour per restricted article, amounting to tens of millions of euros annually in avoidable labour costs. Repositories like ESDS and BADC are estimated to generate annual time efficiency gains in the range of [£68–100 million](#) and [£10–58 million](#), respectively. Additionally, the adoption of text and data mining (TDM) tools under open access conditions may yield [over £150 million](#) annually in productivity improvements.

Transaction costs are also reduced when legal and administrative barriers—such as the need for material transfer agreements—are eliminated, as shown by the [BiOS Initiative](#), which introduced standardized BiOS MTAs to facilitate sharing of biological tools without royalty fees or lengthy negotiations, or projects like [OpenMTA](#).

Finally, open science reduces wasteful duplication of research, particularly in sectors like [pharmaceuticals](#), where multiple firms often unknowingly pursue the same failed targets. Practices like trial preregistration and sharing of negative results can [further enhance efficiency](#) by preventing redundant efforts and directing resources toward more promising avenues.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

Open practices improve labor efficiency—text mining alone saves the UK £150 million annually—and reduce licensing costs, with open data and open access potentially saving tens of millions each year in subscriptions and publication fees.

FOR FUNDERS

Investing in open infrastructure like the Protein Data Bank increases the return on research investments, while initiatives like the OpenMTA reduce administrative burdens, streamlining the sharing of research materials.

Driving Economic Growth

Openly shared scientific data has been linked to substantial economic growth. A 2020 report of the European Union estimates the [open data market size at €184 billion](#) and forecasted it to reach between €199.51 and €334.21 billion in 2025. [Model-based analysis](#) for EMBL-EBI estimated annual R&D returns of £2.2 billion, with a net present value of £9 billion over 30 years, while the [Protein Data Bank](#) contributed an estimated \$1.1 billion annually to global R&D, totaling \$8 billion over three decades.

Although these estimates highlight the high return on investment in open data infrastructures, they are subject to limitations such as attribution challenges and sensitivity to underlying assumptions in economic models.

Open science contributes to economic growth by improving the productivity of R&D investments, as demonstrated through [adaptations of the Solow-Swan growth model](#). Two key parameters—accessibility (the proportion of R&D knowledge available for use) and efficiency (the share of R&D spending generating valuable knowledge)—are used to quantify these effects. The model shows that even modest improvements (e.g., 5% increases in accessibility and efficiency) yield substantial gains, such as \$3 billion annually for Germany and \$5.8 billion for Japan. Subsequent studies in Australia revealed sector-specific benefits, with government R&D alone gaining AUD 165 million per year.

A [recent study](#) provides a comprehensive analysis of the economic significance of open source software (OSS). The study employs unique global data from two complementary sources to assess both the supply-side and demand-side values of OSS. The supply-side value, representing the cost to recreate widely-used OSS, is estimated at \$4.15 billion. In contrast, the demand-side value, reflecting the replacement cost for firms utilizing OSS, is substantially higher at \$8.8 trillion. The research highlights that firms would need to spend 3.5 times more on software in the absence of OSS. Notably, the top six programming languages account for 84% of the demand-side value, and a mere 5% of OSS developers are responsible for 96% of this value.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

The open data market is projected to reach up to €334 billion by 2025, while open source software already drives \$8.8 trillion in demand-side value—highlighting vast commercial potential.

FOR FUNDERS

Open practices can boost public R&D efficiency—already saving billions annually in countries like Germany and Japan—and generate long-term socioeconomic benefits, as seen with digitized natural history collections valued at £2 billion.

Fueling innovation

Empirical evidence from major open data repositories demonstrates that open science infrastructure enables research that would otherwise be impossible to conduct. The value of research enabled by digitisation of natural history collections was estimated to be in excess of [£2 billion](#). [Surveys of users](#) at the European Bioinformatics Institute revealed that 45% of respondents could not have obtained their research data through alternative means. Similarly, approximately 70% of users of the Economic and Social Data Service (UK) [reported](#) they could not have obtained the data in any other way.

The potential for open science to reveal [novel research pathways](#) is particularly evident in text- and data-mining applications. Researchers developed a tool that analyzed literature to identify possible [new disease targets for the drug thalidomide](#), which could then be subject to further research. Such discoveries exemplify how open access to research outputs can generate novel scientific insights that would likely remain undiscovered in traditional, closed research paradigms.

A [recent study](#) demonstrates that open access (OA) mandates significantly impact the diffusion of scientific knowledge into technical inventions, particularly benefiting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The analysis shows that following an OA mandate, patent citations of publicly funded research increased by around 50% among firms with smaller patent portfolios—indicating that access barriers disproportionately affect smaller actors.

SMEs, which are vital to economic output in both the U.S. and Europe, appear to gain the most from improved access to scientific literature. In the same vein, studies [examining open access policies](#) show that removing barriers to scientific literature leads to stronger industry engagement, facilitating knowledge transfer from labs to real-world applications.

Open-source software development, with platforms like Linux and Python, demonstrate how community-driven innovation can outperform proprietary systems in scalability and adaptability. Linux, which powers [over 96%](#) of the world's top 1 million web servers and [dominates the mobile market](#) through Android, illustrates how collaborative, non-proprietary models can underpin critical infrastructure at global scale.

Python, whose popularity has surged due to its versatility and extensive set of libraries and tools, is now the [most-used programming language](#) worldwide according to the 2023 TIOBE Index, and a cornerstone of machine learning and data science development. The adaptability of these platforms is empowered by their open governance and modularity, enabling rapid integration of new technologies and community-led problem-solving.

Similarly, open hardware initiatives present significant economic opportunities. Semico Research predicts that there will be 25 billion RISC-V-based AI SoCs on the market by 2027 with an [expected revenue](#) of \$291 billion that same year. Open hardware gains can also be observed at a smaller scale, like academic [research and development](#) where using an open source hardware design with relatively minor development costs can result in [significant ROIs](#) for the scientific community.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

Open access policies boost SME innovation—patent citations rise by 50% as barriers to research fall. Open source software and platforms like Linux and Python dominate AI and data science, cutting costs and enabling rapid development. Open hardware offers flexibility and projected revenues of \$219B by 2027, while collaborative models like Android show how open ecosystems scale and adapt faster than proprietary ones.

FOR FUNDERS

Open repositories like Zenodo or EMBL-EBI increase research reuse and reduce redundancy, maximizing ROI. Supporting foundational tools like Python delivers long-term value across sectors, and open access policies help level the playing field—empowering SMEs and fostering more inclusive, impactful innovation.

Empowering Enterprise

Open science is a strategic choice that is intelligently reshaping how discoveries are made across fields. In artificial intelligence, open-source frameworks like [TensorFlow](#) and [PyTorch](#) have broadened [access to machine learning tools](#). The life sciences have seen similar acceleration, with the Human Genome Project's open data [reducing sequencing costs](#) from \$100 million to \$600 per genome. Platforms like [Galaxy](#), an open-source bioinformatics workflow system, have transformed computational biology—enabling researchers without coding expertise to carry out sophisticated genomic analyses through shared workflows and standardized tools.

From semiconductors to satellites, open collaboration is driving breakthrough advances across the hardware landscape. In electronics, platforms like [Arduino](#)—an open-source microcontroller system—have enabled rapid prototyping and innovation in sectors ranging from hobbyist robotics to smart agriculture, depending on the specific use case. Agricultural technology has benefited from open climate data enabling predictive crop models and [open-source farm robotics](#) making precision agriculture accessible, while OpenCosmos reduced [satellite deployment costs and time](#) from years to 12-18 months.

Open science approaches [can significantly drive](#) the creation of new products, services, companies, and even industries—particularly in the life sciences or artificial intelligence fields. A flagship example is the release of [ImageNet](#), an openly available, large-scale image dataset that enabled the development of models like AlexNet (2012), which in turn sparked a [surge of new applications](#). Similarly, open source LLMs such as Meta’s [LLaMA](#) models have since become foundational resources for startups and enterprises building custom large language models.

Examples in life sciences include the Structural Genomics Consortium (SGC), [a public-private partnership](#) that openly releases protein structure data without patenting. One notable output is the compound JQ1, which led to GlaxoSmithKline initiating a proprietary drug program that reached clinical trials within two years. [Compared to similar closed compounds](#), JQ1 was associated with a much higher volume of related patents (105 vs. 29). The research also led to three spinouts, including Tensha Therapeutics, [acquired by Roche](#) for \$535 million following an initial \$15 million investment.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

Open approaches reduce costs and speed up R&D by eliminating the need to build proprietary infrastructure (e.g., TensorFlow, Human Genome Project). They enable agile development through hardware flexibility and faster deployment, while also unlocking entirely new markets and business models (e.g., ImageNet, LLaMA, SGC/JQ1).

FOR FUNDERS

Investing in open platforms stimulates innovation and cross-sector collaboration (e.g., ImageNet, Linux, Arduino) while delivering strong returns (e.g., SGC). It also addresses global challenges by supporting solutions with broad societal impact, such as in biosciences and agriculture (e.g., Galaxy, predictive crop models).

OPEN SCIENCE IN ACTION:

PROMOTING SOCIETAL PROGRESS

While the focus of this brief is on the under-considered ways in which open science fuels innovation and growth, it is also important to briefly discuss how open science drives societal progress. The interplay between these two dimensions is significant, as open science strengthens the research ecosystem across social, scientific, economic, and technological dimensions.

This dynamic fosters a reinforcing pattern: transparency and participation [build public trust](#), which in turn supports [broader engagement](#) with research. This, in turn, improves the relevance, rigor, and reach of scientific outputs, [accelerating their translation](#) into real-world applications.

As barriers to innovation drop while participation rises, open science generates [public value](#)—economic opportunities, improved health outcomes, and civic empowerment—that reinforce support for open, collaborative research. This self-reinforcing cycle ensures that open science not only accelerates innovation, but does so in a way that is accountable to, and aligned with, societal needs.

Public Trust and Accountability

Open science helps strengthen [public trust in research](#) by centering transparency and accessibility. When methodologies, data, and findings are openly shared, a broader range of actors—including policymakers, journalists, and the general public—can engage with, scrutinize, and verify scientific claims. Analysis from [Pew Research](#) demonstrates that a clear majority of U.S. adults (57%) trust scientific research findings when data are made publicly available.

A key component of open science is open access (OA), which removes paywalls and licensing restrictions to make research results freely available for reading and reuse. OA is associated with greater accountability by enabling taxpayers, communities, patients, caregivers, practitioners, students, educators, and the general public to [gain better access](#) to the results of publicly funded research. This simple concept – widespread availability of research papers for all – enables meaningful participation, informed debate, and evidence-based policy development.

By extending the reach and utility of research beyond academia, open access increases the legitimacy of scientific institutions while reinforcing their public value. It also creates the conditions under which trust and engagement thrive—laying the groundwork for stronger public support, broader participation, and more effective translation of research into practice. These outcomes, in turn, feed back into the innovation slipstream (helping [small](#) and [large](#) businesses alike), helping to sustain and scale open, collaborative research.

Transparency in Methodology: Legitimacy and Reproducibility

Transparency in research methodology is fundamental to the [legitimacy and credibility](#) of science. When research processes are openly documented and shared, they enable independent verification—long regarded as a cornerstone of scientific rigor. This openness is particularly crucial in the context of the reproducibility crisis, where fields like [psychology](#) and [medicine](#) have responded by adopting practices such as [data sharing](#), and [study preregistration](#) to improve the credibility and reliability of research findings. Similarly, open peer review—where reviewer identities and reports are made public—can increase accountability and foster trust. [Research](#) suggests that this practice can build trust both within scientific communities and among broader audiences.

Transparency also has practical implications for safety and security, [particularly in software development](#). The open-source model, exemplified by systems like Linux and cryptographic tools, shows how publicly accessible code allows for [rapid detection](#) and remediation of vulnerabilities. Collaborative scrutiny strengthens resilience in ways that proprietary approaches often cannot, while saving time and expense by reducing duplication of effort and catching errors earlier.

Leading technology companies have embraced this model to strengthen the global open-source environment. Microsoft, a founding member of the [Open Source Security Foundation \(OpenSSF\)](#), has been instrumental in promoting secure development practices. Through the Alpha-Omega Project—developed in partnership with Google, AWS, RedHat and [many other OpenSSF members](#)—targeted security improvements are made across both high impact ("Alpha") and widely used but lower profile ("Omega") open-source projects. These efforts involve not only direct code improvements but also the advancement of secure coding standards, dependency management tools, and responsible vulnerability disclosure protocols.

By promoting reproducibility, accountability, and secure knowledge infrastructure, open science ensures that scientific outputs are [more trustworthy and actionable](#)—qualities that support their integration into innovation pipelines and policy decisions. In this way, methodological transparency contributes to a feedback loop where rigorous science earns trust, accelerates adoption, and reinforces support for further openness.

Civic Empowerment and Participation

A key way in which open science advances societal progress is by building a deeper and more durable connection between science and society. Open science creates [easy on-ramps](#) to scientific engagement, enabling individuals and communities to both participate in the processes of science and benefit from its outcomes.

This concept of openness drives [related movements](#) such as citizen science (where members of the public actively participate in various stages of the research process, from study design to data collection and analysis) and civic science (which emphasizes the [co-creation of knowledge](#) that is both scientifically rigorous and socially relevant). This inclusivity is both a societal good and a catalyst for [more relevant and impactful science](#).

[Evidence](#) shows that citizen science contributes significantly to the public support for specific topics like [environmental engagement](#), and for [science more generally](#). Studies have [demonstrated](#) that involving non-experts in research improves the science-society relationship by validating local knowledge, making findings more accessible, and affirming public concerns. These collaborative efforts not only [expand the scope and relevance](#) of research but also [build trust](#) through shared ownership and mutual respect.

This civic engagement reinforces the broader open science ecosystem: increased participation improves research outcomes, which in turn deliver more public value and deepen community investment in science. Openness enables wider participation, which in turn can support more responsive and sustained research practices.

KEY TAKEAWAYS

FOR INDUSTRY

Open models and collaborative security initiatives (e.g., Linux, OpenSSF) boost transparency, reduce vulnerabilities, and build trust. Public engagement and use of open data (e.g., in environmental or agricultural applications) strengthen brand value and civic credibility, while shared security frameworks lower risk management costs.

FOR FUNDERS

Supporting open and reproducible research improves transparency and trust in science, while also addressing credibility issues. Supporting inclusive, community-driven projects broadens participation and impact, while open access to biomedical and climate data enables scalable solutions to global health and environmental challenges.

Challenges

Implementing open science strategies delivers clear benefits, but it also inevitably brings its own set of challenges. Organizations and researchers with strong digital infrastructure, funding, and technical expertise are often better positioned to adopt open science practices and translate them into competitive advantage. As open access to data, publications, and tools becomes more common, there is a risk that those already equipped to act quickly may outpace others, [reinforcing existing disparities](#) in capacity and influence.

This dynamic is especially relevant in the context of research commercialization. Universities, driven in part by the priorities of technology transfer offices, have historically pursued patents and exclusive licensing as primary mechanisms for translating research into societal impact and financial return. While these strategies have yielded successes, they can also limit the broader uptake and equitable distribution of publicly funded knowledge. On the opposite end of the spectrum, unrestrained openness, implemented without safeguards or alternative value pathways, could also be significantly flawed. A key risk is that public investment in science will be freely captured by private actors without corresponding public benefit—an issue [well-documented](#) in the literature.

A deliberate, coordinated strategy for open science can address these challenges while still reaping its benefits. By promoting models such as open licensing, universities can [expand their tech transfer portfolio](#) to include more inclusive, lower-barrier pathways for innovation and knowledge use. These alternatives don't have to displace traditional commercialization strategies—they can [coexist](#) with them, particularly in domains where openness [accelerates discovery](#). Thoughtful strategies and collaboration across sectors are essential to ensure that open science not only fuels innovation, but does so in ways that recognize and support the contributions of diverse institutions, regions, and communities.

MOVING FORWARD

Strategic Opportunities

An open-by-design approach to science presents several strategic opportunities that can drive R&D efficiency, economic impact, and societal progress. These opportunities necessitate coordinated efforts across research institutions, funding bodies, policymakers, and industry stakeholders.

A resilient and innovative research culture depends on preserving a core foundation of knowledge, tools, and [infrastructure](#) in the public domain. This ensures that the fruits of science remain accessible, adaptable, and insulated from vendor lock-in. To achieve this, public and private funders, the private sector, governments, and institutions of higher learning must prioritize sustained, scalable, coordinated investment in a range of open science activities, including open access publishing, [FAIR](#)-compliant data repositories, and the long-term maintenance of open-source software and hardware.

The proactive development and adoption of shared interoperability standards are equally essential to avoid technological silos and ensure that open systems remain truly open—capable of evolving, integrating, and supporting wide participation in the production and application of knowledge.

[Open science infrastructure](#) today is supported by a diverse set of academic, nonprofit, and industry actors working to enable open access to research data, tools, and knowledge.

In Europe, for example, the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#), and [OpenAIRE](#) provide federated platforms and services for open data sharing and policy implementation. In life sciences, [ELIXIR](#) coordinates bioinformatics infrastructure across European countries, while the [Structural Genomics Consortium \(SGC\)](#) exemplifies open biomedical research by releasing structural data without patents. Computational access is facilitated by platforms like the [Open Science Grid \(OSG\)](#), which provides distributed high-throughput computing for scientific research. In the U.S., the [National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource \(NAIRR\)](#) aims to democratize access to AI tools through public-private partnerships.

On the industry side, the [Open Source Security Foundation \(OpenSSF\)](#), led by the Linux Foundation and supported by Microsoft, Google, and others, works to advance the adoption of open-source software. Nonprofits like the [Open Commons Consortium \(OCC\)](#) and [Renaissance Computing Institute \(RENCI\)](#) provide cloud-based data commons and manage tools like iRODS to support data-intensive research collaboration.

Policy alignment and incentive restructuring will further accelerate the transition toward open science. Current research evaluation systems often prioritize proprietary outputs over open collaboration, creating misaligned incentives. Policymakers and funding agencies can expand open access mandates to encompass not only publications but also data, code, and methodologies. [Public-private partnerships](#) around technology transfer models based on open source are key in this direction.

Open Source Program Offices (OSPOs) are dedicated organizational units within academic institutions, companies, and government agencies that coordinate, support, and govern open-source activities. They play a strategic role in managing open source contributions, ensuring license compliance, promoting best practices, and aligning open initiatives with institutional goals. In industry, OSPOs are widely adopted by tech leaders—[Google](#), [Microsoft](#), and [Red Hat](#)—to systematically engage with and contribute to open source ecosystems.

In academia, initiatives like the [OSPO++ network](#) foster collaboration between university-based OSPOs, such as those at Johns Hopkins University and the University of Vermont, promoting the integration of open source into research, education, and civic technology. The European Commission has also established its own [EU Open Source Program Office](#), signaling institutional commitment to open technologies in the public sector. Collectively, OSPOs institutionalize openness, providing structure and sustainability to the growing role of open source in driving innovation.

Training and capacity-building initiatives are essential to mainstreaming open science practices and can be professionalized to ensure consistency and quality. Graduate curricula and professional development programs can better incorporate standardized training in open data management, reproducible research methods, and collaborative tools, fostering a culture of transparency from the outset. Standardized open science training and partnerships with industry leaders can boost [opportunities for talent recruitment](#), ensuring researchers are not only equipped with essential skills but also recognized for their expertise in open science inside and outside academia.

NASA's Transform to Open Science (TOPS) initiative stands out with its comprehensive [Open Science 101](#) curriculum, a free, five-module course designed to equip researchers, students, and the public with foundational open science principles and practices. In the nonprofit sector, the [Center for Open Science](#) offers tools and training to foster open research practices. The [Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences \(BITSS\)](#) provides training and resources to advance open research practices in social sciences. The [Open Science Framework \(OSF\)](#) offers tools and training to support researchers in managing and sharing their work openly.

The [Open Source Security Foundation \(OpenSSF\)](#), hosted by the Linux Foundation, collaborates with industry leaders like Microsoft and Google to improve the security of open-source software through training and best practices. [GitHub Education](#) offers free resources, tools, and partnerships on open-source and project-based learning. Platforms like [The Carpentries](#) or [Programming Historian](#) provide domain-specific open research tutorials. Additionally, platforms like [edX](#) and [Coursera](#) partner with universities and organizations to provide massive open online courses (MOOCs) on topics related to open science and open source development.

Robust frameworks for measuring and communicating the impact of open science are needed to assess strategies and secure sustained institutional and financial support. While qualitative benefits—such as increased collaboration and public trust—are widely acknowledged, quantitative evidence of cost savings, innovation acceleration, and economic returns can strengthen the case for investment.

Case studies demonstrating tangible outcomes—such as the role of open data in reducing R&D redundancies or the economic spillovers from open-source software—can further illustrate the value proposition of open science to policymakers and industry leaders. Public-private partnerships can lead to common frameworks to allow data generation to enable comparisons and evaluation of open science strategies.

Highlights

Two initiatives advancing open science monitoring are the [PathOS](#) project and the [Global Research Initiative on Open Science \(GRIOS\)](#). The PathOS project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe program, has developed the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook, which provides a comprehensive framework for assessing the academic, societal, and economic impacts of open science practices. The [handbook](#) emphasizes a causal approach to understanding the effects of open science and offers operational guidance for implementing various indicators.

CALL TO ACTION

To fully harness the promise of open science, we must build beyond fragmented initiatives toward a more coordinated, strategic, and boundary-spanning approach. Realizing the economic and societal potential of openness will require collaboration across sectors—aligning research institutions, funders, technologists, industry leaders, and policymakers around shared goals and scalable solutions. In today's environment, it is increasingly critical to establish common norms, produce actionable guidance, and spotlight real-world success stories that reaffirm a vision of open science grounded in rigor, transparency, and shared benefit.

This collaboration begins with dialogue. There is a pressing need for trusted spaces where academia, government, and industry can candidly exchange ideas and identify aligned opportunities. Such a venue could facilitate the joint development and maintenance of open data platforms, contributor frameworks, and licensing models, all centered on openness as a driver of innovation and societal progress. Beyond creating a space to share and learn, this community approach can provide tangible value in other critical ways: strategic guidance on emerging policy, access to expert insights, early intelligence on trends in open science and technology, and collaborative mechanisms for funding and piloting new approaches.

By investing in this kind of coalition building, we can support a shift beyond fragmented open science initiatives toward a more coordinated, strategic, and boundary-spanning approach—reducing barriers, improving public trust, and facilitating the application of research findings. This is not merely about expanding access to knowledge, but about designing an intentional approach to R&D that is more efficient, connected, resilient, and responsive to the challenges and opportunities of our time.

Glossary of Terms

- AlphaFold: An AI system developed by DeepMind that predicts protein structures with high accuracy, demonstrating the potential of open models for scientific discovery.
- APACE: A framework integrating AlphaFold2 with advanced computing to accelerate protein structure prediction.
- Citizen Science: Scientific research conducted, in whole or in part, by amateur or non-professional scientists—often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists.
- Civic Science: An approach to science that emphasizes co-creation of knowledge between researchers and the public, aiming for socially relevant and scientifically rigorous outcomes.
- FAIR Principles: Guidelines that promote data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable to maximize the use and value of research data.
- ImageNet: A large, publicly available visual database used to train AI models, critical in the development of deep learning and computer vision systems.
- LLM (Large Language Model): A type of AI model trained on vast amounts of text data capable of generating human-like language; examples include Meta's LLaMA.
- NAIRR (National AI Research Resource): A U.S. initiative to provide shared access to computational resources and data for AI research.
- Open Access (OA): The practice of making research outputs freely available online, removing paywalls and access barriers.
- OpenAIRE: An EU initiative providing infrastructure and services to support open access and open science in Europe.
- Open Compute Project (OCP): An open-source hardware initiative that redesigns hardware to support more efficient, scalable computing infrastructure.
- OpenMTA (Open Material Transfer Agreement): A legal framework facilitating the open sharing of biological materials between institutions.
- Open Science: A broad movement to make scientific research—including data, methods, publications, and tools—openly accessible and reusable.
- Open Science Grid (OSG): A distributed computing platform providing high-throughput computing resources for scientific research.

- OpenSSF (Open Source Security Foundation): An organization supported by the Linux Foundation and major tech companies focused on improving open-source software security.
- Open Source Software (OSS): Software with source code that is freely available for anyone to view, use, modify, and distribute.
- OSPO (Open Source Program Office): Organizational units in companies, governments, or universities that coordinate and govern open-source strategies and compliance.
- PathOS: An EU-funded project creating tools to measure the impact of open science, including the Open Science Impact Indicator Handbook.
- Protein Data Bank (PDB): An open-access database that archives 3D structural data of biological molecules, critical for biomedical and pharmaceutical research.
- PyTorch / TensorFlow: Popular open-source machine learning frameworks that support AI development across academia and industry.
- RISC-V: An open standard instruction set architecture for CPUs that allows developers to design and use processors without proprietary restrictions.
- SGC (Structural Genomics Consortium): A public-private partnership that openly shares data and tools to accelerate drug discovery without pursuing patents.
- SMEs (Small and Medium-sized Enterprises): Businesses with a limited number of employees and revenue, often highlighted as major beneficiaries of open access to scientific resources.
- TOPS (Transform to Open Science): A NASA initiative that provides open science training and promotes open practices within the scientific community.
- Zenodo: An open-access repository developed by CERN that allows researchers to share datasets, software, and publications freely.

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